

RELIGION, POLITICS AND CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC IN NIGERIA

By

SAMUEL ENEOJO AKWU

akwusamuelenejo@gmail.com

Department of Religious Studies,

Faculty of Arts and Humanities,

Kogi State University, Anyigba, Nigeria

AND

OKENYI KENNETH SUNDAY, Ph.D

Department of Philosophy,

University of Nigeria,

Nsukka

08071627888

And

ADAMA REUBEN CHIMAObI, Ph.D

Department of Religious Studies,

Faculty of Arts and Humanities,

Kogi State University, Anyigba,

Nigeria

Email: reubenadama565@gmail.com

Phone: 08066232001 or 09026858000

Abstract

This paper analyzed the Coronavirus pandemic phenomena that have been the latest threat facing the entire globe since 2019-2020. The virus, along with its resulting terrible effects, is said to have spread rapidly across the world. Hundreds of thousands of people are thought to have been killed and many have been left in unexpected isolation centers in an effort to monitor, curb and contain the further spread of the virus. The worst of all is the worldwide lockdown of all areas of human organizations in an effort to prevent the virus from spreading further. Among others, the economic sector's lockdown has continued to pose cogs for human survival. The World Health Organisation and The pandemic has been rated as the worst in human history by medical experts. Many research on the pandemic

are underway and this has given rise to a good number of hypotheses about the causes of the pandemic. Although some people embrace the pandemic as a natural occurrence, others maintain the stance that it is man-made to the detriment of human life through ulterior motives for social influence. The paper seeks to analyze and explain some of the complexities and doubts that cloud these phenomena from the perspective of religion through historical, phenomenological and analytical methods, particularly the church, which raises some concerns based on a number of prophecies and predictions on the incoming pandemic within the church for centuries.

Background

Human history is experiencing a very strange period battling a dreaded enemy: the novel Coronavirus Covid-19. Initially detected in China's Wuhan province, now quickly spreading throughout the world. The World Health Organization (WHO) announced on 23 September 2012 the discovery of a new coronavirus, MERS-Covid, in two patients who died in the Middle East due to a mysterious, rapidly lethal disease (Zaki. A.M: Van Boheemen S, Besterbroer T.M, Osterhaus A.D, Fouchier R.A, 2012).

This is not to suggest that only in 2012 the viruses became recognized, but the Corona Virus was in nature, and for some decades ago several inquiries were underway on it. However, it has not resorted to a pandemic as it is today, despite its presence for almost a century. Coronaviruses are associated with a large range of human and other animal diseases, according to Weiner (1987). The author argues that since the first international congress in Germany in 1980, the importance of this group of viruses in both medical and economic terms has become increasingly evident. Over the past few years, the number of investigators has risen as justification for this congress, which is the largest ever conducted (Weiner 1987) to date.

From the very first day of coronavirology, the appeal to veterinary, medical and basic scientists probably revolved around the marked tropism these viruses had for specific tissues, particularly the gastrointestinal tract, respiratory system, and nervous system. Baude and Hudson possibly made the first scientific discoveries in 1933 when they identified chickens'"gasping illness" and then transmitted the

illness to embryos. A devastatingly fatal respiratory disease has been observed to be the gasping disease (Baudelte F.R, and Hudson, C.B, 1937: Gledhill A.W, Andrews C.H, 1951).

Recently, the virus is said to belong to a family of viruses that can cause different symptoms, such as pneumonia, fever, trouble breathing, and lung infections. These viruses are not odd, yet are widespread in animals worldwide, although very few cases have been known to affect humans until recently, according to experts. Wuhan Municipal Commission for Health and Welfare (WMHC) briefing on the current.

World Health Organization (WHO) used the term 2019 novel Coronavirus to refer to a Coronavirus that affected the lower respiratory tract of patients with pneumonia in Wuhan, China on 29th December, 2019. The WHO announced that the official name of the 2019 novel Coronavirus is Coronavirus disease (Covid-19). And the current reference name for the virus is severe acute respiratory syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-Covid-2). (CDC 2019 Novel Coronavirus, Wuhan China 2020: WHO. Novel Coronavirus, Wuhan, China 2020).

COVs have been identified in both avian and various mammals, including bats, camels, dogs and masked palm civets, and are previously regarded as pathogens that only cause mild disease in the immunocompetent people until the emergence of the Coronavirus causing severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS-COV0 in late 2002. Currently, atleast seven Coronavirus species are known to cause disease in humans. The viruses emerged in strange form in December 2019 in Wuhan, China and a great effort is being undertaken to contain its spreading Kraziek *et al* 1966)

There is evidence that Coronavirus spreads from person to person, but good hygiene can prevent the infection (Chavis & Ganesh, 2020: chen et al, 2020: Peng 2020). The outbreak has since spread to all provinces mainline China and 27 other countries, with more than 1.300,000 confirmed cases and over 230,000 confirmed deaths as of May 20, 2020 (World Health Organization (WHO), 2020). According to a report by WHO (2020), the speed of transmission for Covid-19 virus is estimated to be 5-6 days: the reproductive number is said to be between 2 and 2.5: children are less infected than adults. Currently, the crude mortality ratio

is between 3-4%. While a number of therapeutics are in clinical trials in China and more than 20 vaccines in development there are presently no licensed vaccines or therapeutics available (Olaniyi, 2020).

Fear abounds about the novel Pandemic of Coronavirus and the implications. The number of recorded deaths is rising. These figures are projected to rise as attention is given to indirect costs due to reduced production and co-morbidities. Thus, the economic effects are adverse not only to the public health system, but also to trade and transport, the food and agriculture sectors, different types of markets and retail chains, among others. Proactive management approaches, a health policy system addressing many of the social determinants of health, education and health literacy, national and international funding changes, public and private collaborations and the creation of a World Coronavirus Technical Council are among the policy options proposed. Successful implementation of these policy solutions would require full support from stakeholders, including governments, the media, NGOs, health practitioners, communities, and individuals (Olaniyi, 2020).

The rise of the pandemic has prompted all world governments to begin strategizing about how to get the pandemic under control and its malevolent impact. But despite all these efforts, the pandemic has remained unabated, given that health is central to a productive, healthy society, while panic and disease can impede any society's development, consumption, leisure, travel, and overall well-being (Marin 2017: Adeola & Evans 2018: Lawanson & Evans, 2019, etc.). All hands are on deck around the board due to the immense catastrophic effects of this pandemic to prevent it from taking its full course in any given environment.

There have been so many controversies among politicians, religious leaders / clergy members, academic and lay members of society in the efforts of governments, especially African governments and Nigerian government in particular to arrive at certain decisions in the bid to contain the coronavirus pandemic. This is because, for their ugly attitudes of playing with something that should be treated with utmost seriousness, African leaders are renowned. Giving the problem at hand a careful perspective, one can rather find that in their leadership nature, African leaders are more puzzled. Some of the Nigerian government's pandemic policies explicitly show that they have altered

motivations above or below the real issue on the ground. This has contributed to the existence of conflicting views among people as to whether or not there is a coronavirus, whether or not it occurs only in Europe, or whether or not all reports about the pandemic are man-made or not.

The aim of this paper is not to focus much on scientific explanation on the issues of the pandemic from this elucidated background, but to kindly evaluate from the angle of religion, especially the church, on some controversial issues around the pandemic (coronavirus) as they affect human society, religion in general, and the church in particular.

Theories on Origin and Causes of Coronavirus

When it comes to the roots of the novel coronavirus, there are several hypotheses doing the rounds. Where it must have originated from is the best debate on the subject. The coronavirus is widely thought to have originated in China. Almost everyone and all has embraced this stand. Although many people agreed and sympathize with the Chinese government on what they felt was the result of a botched experiment, leading to the first touch of the early patients (victims) in the seafood in Wuhan, the US authorities believed and assumed that the pandemic was a Bio weapon intended by the Chinese government to reverse and weaken American positions rather than a mistake or botched experiment. The Chinese were later accused of intending to be the world superpower; a war they have lost in so many respects (Marlin 2017). Two wide hypotheses can be deduced from the foregoing: (i) the coronavirus' natural origin and (ii) the virus' deliberate or man-made origin as a bioweapon. Scientists are divided on these two theories; while some accept its natural emergence, others are of the opinion that it is a missile, or even if it is natural, it has been deliberately mismanaged by the Chinese authorities for some subsequent reasons. Let's take a look at the two wide theories in the following passage:

I. Natural origin of the Pandemic

Coronavirus (covid-19) is a zoonotic disease, according to the WHO. Diseases which are or can be transmitted between animals and humans are said to be zoonotic diseases. The movement of pathogens from animals to humans presents a major threat to human health. Our lack of previous exposure means that when

the symptoms are serious, humans do not have any established antibodies to protect themselves against the diseases. Recent outbreaks of zoonotic diseases include: H1N1 or Swine Flu (2009): Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS (2012): Ebola (2014-2015): Zika virus (2015-2016): and West African Nile virus (2019). Severe acute or bird flu (2004): The global patterns of nearly a century confirm that zoonotic disease outbreaks occur more regularly (UN Environment Programme Report 2016, UNEP). The study also suggests that zoonoses are real problems of global concern. The study went on to state that "three new infectious diseases occur in humans on average per year: 75% of all emerging infectious diseases in humans are now zoonotic." It is not shocking for scientists to have a coronavirus pandemic in 2019-2020, based on this scientific forecast since 2012. What is shocking, though, is the pace at which it has spread and killed people around the world.

A large number of scientists advocate the natural origin hypothesis of the virus. The virus naturally appeared in Wuhan in 2019 as a zoonotic disease, according to these researchers. The scientists engaged in experiments with bat coronavirus, including so-called gene splicing, in Wuham, a "region in China," and the virus escaped and infected humans. Another version of this hypothesis is that there was sloppy safety among laboratory workers and a wild virus was released in procedures, perhaps in the collection or disposal of animal specimens (WMHC 2020). Some have hypothesized on social media that humans may have contacted the virus through familiar and regular encounters or interactions between humans and animals, apart from the suggestion of human associations with wild animals with coronavirus, which is very popular among the Chinese, Indians and Europeans in recent times (Drosten et al 1967). The social media is full of accounts of many marriage ties, Among Europeans and Asian people, sexual encounters and pets with or around wild life. Speculations still hold that, as a result of these interactions, the coronavirus is potentially zoonotic. Some of the social media speculations say that, as between Indians and Chinese, raw eating of wild animals may have been another means of communication with the virus.

The theory of natural origin holds that the virus may have originated spontaneously through the zoonotic mechanism of transfer of the virus from animals to humans and that some people may not want it man-made. A lot of

scientific evidence confirms this. For instance, during a camera press briefing at the Pentagon Joint Chiefs Chairman on May 5, 2020, General Mark Milley said "we don't know whether the outbreak began in Chinese laboratories or wet markets." He added that the weight of proof is that it was normal and not produced by man. Scientists from many countries have said that evidence indicates that the virus came from animals, not a laboratory, and most intelligence agencies remain doubtful that evidence can also be found to demonstrate any laboratory argument. A few scientists have proposed that one of the researchers in the laboratory may have inadvertently contaminated the virus, but many scientists have discounted the hypothesis (the New York Times Report on April 30). The scientific opinion denying the idea that the virus was engineered is almost universal, in addition to the evidence above against the idea that the virus was engineered. A team in California led by microbiology professor Kristian Andeisen said in a letter to nature in March 2020 that "the genetic evidence irrefutably shows that (covid-19) is not derived from any previously used virus backbone," i.e. "spliced parts of another recognized virus." It was much more likely, they concluded, that the virus spontaneously originated and became stronger through natural selection. The team suggested two hypotheses that can plausibly explain the origin of sars-cov-20: natural selection before zoonotic (animal to human) transition in the animal host: and natural selection after zoonotic transition in humans.

In support of the natural origin of coronavirus, Mr. Ben Embarek, a WHO expert on animal to human disease transmission, and other experts have clarified to the Guardian that if the virus had been modified, you would expect to see evidence in both gene sequences and distortion in the mutation family tree data, a so-called "reticulation" effect. In another comment to the Guardian, on the suggestion promoting the theory that the virus was engineered, James Le Duc, the director of the Galveston National Laboratory in the U.S., the most active bio containment on a US Academic Campus, even poured cold water. He added that, "There is compelling evidence that the new virus was not the result of deliberate genetic modification and, given its strong resemblance to other known bat-associated coronaviruses, it almost certainly emerged from nature." This supports the scientific stance that SARS, MERS and EBOLA Virus are thought to be natural hosts for bats. It is assumed in some quotas that through Cat-like Civets, SARS

ourbreak got to humans from Bats, but MERS-Cov spread from bats to camels and then to humans. However, in the case of Covid-19, some of the newly published studies refer to scaly, ant-eating pangolins as the intermediate species between bats and humans. It is clear from the foregoing that, as a hypothesis, the natural origin of the coronavirus received more support among scientists and researchers than the idea of the virus being engineered by a good number of people as postulated. This is because there is overwhelming scientific proof for this stance.

The Conspiracy Theory (Manmade origin of the Coronavirus)

Numerous Facebook conspiracy groups, Obscure Twitter accounts, promoted the idea that the virus was man-made and even found its way to PrimeTV Russian State. Government leaders, senior politicians and media outlets in China and the US have been supporting these claims.

Such claims have been more accepted in Africa, particularly Nigeria, by a good number of politicians, scholars and religious boundaries, particularly the politicians of the church. The first body to assert the virus as man-made was the officials of the US government. First of all, they see the virus outbreak as a bio-weapon, designed against the hegemony of the US government by the Chinese government. They took this position enthusiastically because they were in a deadlog with the Chinese government in a battle for world power.

It is also important to note that the US was also alleged to have released the weapon within the framework of the conspiracy theory. The idea that Covid-19 may have emerged in the US has been repeatedly promoted by Mr. Zhao Lijian, a Chinese spokesman for the foreign ministry. He claimed that the outbreak was developed and released to China by American power through a Canadian researcher so that America could accuse China of being responsible for it. He said in a tweet on March 12th that it may have been the U.S. army that carried the virus to Wuhan. One day later, he tweeted an article titled "Further proof that the virus originated in the US" on the Global Research website, and encouraged people to read and share it.

The Global Times, the Chinese daily, echoed Mr. Zhao's sentiment. A number of Chinese embassies and social media users in various parts of the world have also

amplified his claims. It is worth noting that these allegations and counter-accusations between the US and Chinese governments have led, among so many groups of people, to many contentious social media discussions. On this note, continuous claims made individuals begin to assume that the virus can be manmade. It is from this point of view that it is said that the pandemic is a politically initiated instrument for certain ulterior social control motives. Another variant of the hypothesis of the arrival of the coronavirus in favor of man averred that the pandemic is neither from China nor the US, but that it is coordinated by some high-ranking individuals in developed countries, with a pre-planned idea of using the virus and its results, perhaps its mode of vaccination as the remedy provided, to shift the world order from old to new. Through the 5G network growth, this is arranged to be modified.

It is suspected that the system's test run in China tends to be malevolent to the human body, contributing to the human body's imono-competency, rendering humans vulnerable to coronavirus infection. It is the concept and conviction that the pandemic can be man-made that takes this pandemic into the theological dimension. While, as it is now, the man-made hypothesis has come under assault from scientists and liberal minds, it is also clear from proof that there are human undertones to the pandemic's emergence. Let's make brief in the next passage a look at why religion must support the idea of man-made theory.

Religion, Politics and Coronavirus Pandemic in Nigeria

In recent times, among Western developed countries, there has been so much assault on religion. In fact, nothing like religion in Europe has been repelled so much in recent times. Religious practices are seen as phenomena by contemporary European countries, intended to be experienced by nations that are yet to evolve completely and that if one is sophisticatedly developed, there is no need to proceed with religion. Via several current theories in scholarship and general behavioral patterns of people, this attitude is commonly shared among European nations. Christianity is the most criticized religion in Europe. A large number of bills made into law under President Bill Clinton and Obama, for example, were completely anti-Christian in nature.

There were many social policies that were polarized in Christianity against such scriptural evidence, such as abortion equality, gay rights, bisexual rights, bestialism, etc. Even presidents have strongly endorsed these and several others who claimed to be Christians. There are the reasons why Christians and religious people believe that one of the mechanized methods to destroy Christianity's spread is the pandemic.

Among religious leaders, particularly Christian clergymen in Nigeria and Africa at large, the man-made theory gained a lot of acceptance. In the book of Revelation, the church was conscious of several eschatological prophecies and some projections regarding the end times in the early church by men of God. The anti-Christ is believed to come with the goal of unifying the government of the world, as well as creating one faith for the world as a whole. So, the notion of social control as one of the pandemic's theories of origin jolted the church into reasoning that it could be time for such prophecy to come to pass, causing a lot of addo to this knowledge among Christians.

There have been many projections of a pandemic coming up in the 21st century and precisely in the year 2020, aside from the prophecies. In certain cases, the forecasts explicitly indicated that the pandemic will be man-made. In view of these, among most evangelicals, mainline churches and some of the Catholics and Pentecostals, it is assumed that even though the virus itself is not man-made, world leaders mismanage it to the detriment of humanity. The test run of the 5 G technical system is the most speculated one of the world networks. Pastor Chris Oyakhilome of the Embassy of Christ is one of the advocates of this view.

On channel TV, the pastor publicly claimed that the epidemic or pandemic was man-made and that the world forces are using 5 G to put the whole world system under their influence. He called upon all stakeholders and religious bodies, advocated by Bill Gate and his cohorts, to oppose the change. Bishop David Oyedepo, the presiding bishop of Living Faith Church worldwide is another church voice. According to him, he said the pandemic was from the pit of hell in one of his Sunday worship services on his Breakthrough television, planned to destabilize God's will for the Church. At another time, he criticized 5 G technology because of its future ability to transmit the virus. Papa Adeboye Enoch, a front line church leader, also made several plausible claims about the

origin of the virus."In his words," the virus is not man-made in any country, but God's way of punishing the whole world for all kinds of bloodshed, murder, injustice and oppression, and various kinds of atrocities happening in the world.

There are also other men of God who echo the postulations of these Pentecostal fathers, lending their voices. But in general, from the eschatological perspective, the church sees the pandemic as confirmation intended to put the world to an end. Bill Gate, Obama, Clinton and a good number of liberal minds in the US, particularly members of the Democratic Party, are now being accused by the church in Nigeria and Africa as brains behind the Covid-19. They accused them of endorsing anti-Christian operations that occurred long before the pandemic. The operations of the WHO, NCDS etc, as several of the practices and modes of operation of these bodies remain suspect, they have not been taken for granted in this respect. For instance, well before the pandemic, there was outcry about the potential impacts of the 5 G technology that is capable of causing harm to the human body system (Adeola and Evans 2018). Even prior to the Covid 19 pandemic, a good number of individuals raised alarm to that effect, but all of these were in vain. The 5 G technology was tested in Abuja (Maitama), Lagos (Ikeja) and South Africa respectively during this lockdown, according to Pst Christ in his previously described speech. The lockdown and social distancing was intended for the free implantation of the 5 G system in his argument, and that people would not be able to unite to protest against this evil act against humanity.

Conclusion

The paper investigated, from a theological viewpoint, the phenomenon of the coronavirus pandemic. It is true that the pandemic has placed the entire planet into chaos with its apparent dreadful implications. The World Health Organization ranks it as the worst of its kind in human history. The investigator made several moves in this paper to test the hypotheses on the causes of this pandemic. This is because its nature excites the most fervent discussion of all the mysteries about the new coronavirus. Different hypotheses were extensively investigated on its existence; natural evolution against the theory of its man-made existence. It is evident from this research that while the theory of natural evolution seems to gain a lot of support among academics and scientists with more data, there is no denying the fact that some of the world powers have mismanaged knowledge

about the pandemic. This condition has raised many controversial challenges to its natural origin, including the church's stance that the pandemic has been massively mismanaged to the detriment of mankind in general and the church in particular, if it is not man-made. Several uncertainties which led the church to this conclusion have been duly recognized in this paper.

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